

Project Title	Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice
Project Acronym	WorldFAIR
Grant Agreement No	101058393
Instrument	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01
Topic, type of action	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41 HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Start Date of Project	2022-06-01
Duration of Project	24 months
Project Website	http://worldfair-project.eu

D5.1 Formalisation of OneGeochemistry

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Due Date	30.11.2022
Date	30.11.2022
Version	1.3 DRAFT NOT YET APPROVED BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7380947

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
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Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	31.10.2022	Alexander Prent, Rebecca Farrington, Lesley Wyborn, Kerstin Lehnert, Dominik Hezel, Kirsten Elger, Lucia Profeta	Inclusion of OneGeochemistry Interim Board D5.1-specific meeting notes (meetings of 13 & 28.10.22)
0.2	01.11.2022	Alexander Prent, Geertje ter Maat	Draft edited to follow outline and (example) questions
0.3	14.11.2022	Alexander Prent, Marthe Klöcking, Lesley Wyborn	Extending draft, including feedback and comments
1.0	16.11.2022	Alexander Prent, Marthe Klöcking, Lesley Wyborn	Draft 1 ready, inc. all sub-chapters, review MK
1.1	25.11.2022	Quentin Groom, Simon Hodson, Ana Ortigoza	Draft revisions
1.2	29.11.2022	Alexander Prent, Lesley Wyborn	Inclusion of feedback, changes

1.3	30.11.2022	Alexander Prent, Simon Hodson	Content ready
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WorldFAIR has received funding from the European Commission's WIDERA coordination and support programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101058393. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Terms and Abbreviations

Geochemistry	The study of the chemical composition of the Earth and solid bodies in the solar system, their rocks and minerals, including the distribution, circulation and abundance of elements their ions and isotopes, molecules and fluids
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
CODATA	The International Science Council Committee on Data
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
QA/QC	Quality Assurance / Quality Control
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative

Executive Summary

The WorldFAIR Geochemistry Work Package Deliverable 5.1 sets out to formalise the OneGeochemistry Initiative. With the exponential growth of data volumes and production, better coordination and collaboration is needed within the Earth and Planetary Science community producing geochemical data. The mission of OneGeochemistry is to address this need and in order to do so effectively the [OneGeochemistry Interim Board](#) has applied to become the OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group. This application has been approved by the CODATA Executive Committee. The OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group will be led by a chair and co-chair and will form expert advisory groups where required. Becoming a CODATA Working Group gives the OneGeochemistry Initiative credibility and authority to successfully pursue a long-term governance structure and accomplish the other WorldFAIR deliverables of WP05 (Geochemistry).

Accomplishing an outline of the methodology used to populate and update FAIR Implementation Profiles and to promulgate knowledge of them, as well as creating a set of guidelines for laboratories and repositories on how to use FAIR Implementation Profiles and common variables to QA/QC data, will enable FAIRer (Wilkinson et al., 2016) geochemical data, which will in turn make interdisciplinary use easier.

Geochemical data has direct application to six of the seventeen UN Sustainable Development Goals (*SDG#6 (Clean Water and Sanitation); SDG#7 (Affordable and Clean Energy); SDG#8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth); SDG#9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure); SDG#13 (Climate Action); SDG#15 (Life on Land)*) and FAIR geochemical data will accelerate the generation of new geoscientific knowledge and discoveries. Within the greater framework of the WorldFAIR project, this deliverable has come together in collaboration with CODATA (WP01 and WP02) and the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC, WP03).

Table of contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	6
1.1. Background – Current state of geochemistry	6
1.2. Innovation – OneGeochemistry initiative as solution	6
1.3. Implications – Scope of formal OneGeochemistry WG	7
2. Rationale, Structure and Activities	8
3. Conclusion	11
4. Bibliography and web resources	13
5. Appendix 1	15

1. Introduction

The first deliverable (D5.1) by the WorldFAIR Geochemistry Work Package (WP05) aims to formalise the OneGeochemistry Initiative, in order to effectively address the need for better coordination and collaboration within the Earth and Planetary Science community producing geochemical data. As such, the OneGeochemistry Interim Board has applied and was approved by the CODATA Executive Committee to become the OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group for the next two years.

Within this formal Working Group, the OneGeochemistry Initiative will develop a governance structure upon which the initiative can build into the future as well as engage and connect with key stakeholders from the global community.

This document is the result of consultation within the current OneGeochemistry Initiative and its Interim Board to design an appropriate mechanism to formalise the initiative. The input comes from globally active data management system leaders, large research and data infrastructure experts and coordinators, geochemical analytical facilities and related data production capabilities ([EarthChem^e](#), [DIGIS-GEOROC^d](#), [AGN-AusGeochem^a](#), [GFZ Data Services^g](#), [NFDI4Earthⁿ](#), and [EPOS^{ep}](#)) as well as from the geochemistry community (Klöcking et al., pre-print).

1.1. Background – Current state of geochemistry

The Earth and Planetary Science community is producing geochemical data at an increasing rate and volume. In order to advance geoscientific knowledge and discoveries, and solve complex research questions, large and often global data compilations require analysis and synthesis. The diverse nature of geochemical data and differences in data reporting between institutes and laboratories prove to be significant hurdles in the compilation of large datasets. Combined with advances in research capabilities (instruments and methods) and increased variety of data types analysed, these developments necessitate better coordination and collaboration within the geochemistry community around data curation and stewardship.

1.2. Innovation – OneGeochemistry initiative as solution

An informal international initiative - the OneGeochemistry Initiative - was recently formed as a collaboration between multiple globally-distributed organisations that support geochemistry capability and data production. The OneGeochemistry Initiative seeks to create a global geochemical data network that facilitates and promotes discovery of, and access to, geochemical data through coordination and collaboration among international geochemical data providers. The OneGeochemistry mission is to advance geoscientific knowledge and discoveries by building and

maintaining consensus-driven standards that make geochemistry research data globally findable and accessible, and truly interoperable and reusable to both humans and machines (FAIR; Wilkinson et al., 2016). When provenance, methodology and a measure of data quality are consistently documented others will be enabled to trust, interpret and reuse data.

As OneGeochemistry focuses on globally coordinating geochemistry data standardisation efforts of a diverse community it fills a niche previously unoccupied. Standardisation efforts have nearly always focused on national, programmatic or less centralised levels and there is little knowledge of which standards have been developed. Where standards exist, they are mostly available as journal publication PDF files from multiple organisations and sites; few enable data to be FAIR and are shared globally. There are five International Science Council Unions, multiple international commissions, programs, societies, associations (Appendix 1), as well as national equivalents that can contribute. Yet currently there is insufficient coordination between them to collaboratively address the issue of FAIR geochemical data. Formalisation of the OneGeochemistry Initiative is hence warranted to address the need for coordination and better collaboration.

1.3. Implications – Scope of formal OneGeochemistry WG

The formalisation of the OneGeochemistry Initiative as OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group will give OneGeochemistry credibility and authority to successfully pursue long-term governance structure and accomplish the other WorldFAIR deliverables of the Geochemistry Work Package (WP05). The WG will outline the methodology used to populate and update FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and promulgate knowledge of them as well as creating a set of guidelines for laboratories and repositories on how to use FIPs and common variables to QA/QC data. This will enable FAIRer (Wilkinson et al., 2016) geochemical data, which will make interdisciplinary use easier. Geochemical data has direct application to six of the seventeen UN Sustainable Development Goals (*SDG#6 (Clean Water and Sanitation); SDG#7 (Affordable and Clean Energy); SDG#8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth); SDG#9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure); SDG#13 (Climate Action); SDG#15 (Life on Land); Figure 1*) and FAIR geochemical data will accelerate the generation of new geoscientific knowledge and discoveries.

A formal OneGeochemistry Initiative and its endorsement by societies and associations will enable OneGeochemistry to develop and promote influential, global, community-driven data conventions and best practices necessary to build a global network of high-quality, trusted geochemical data. As a formal initiative, OneGeochemistry will consult the geochemistry community and the other WorldFAIR Work Packages about essential research object description fields (metadata), research protocols, schemas and vocabularies, from which to create common minimum standards. Most

WorldFAIR work packages and partners will benefit from such efforts as many have a core research object (to which all future data collections are linked); many WPs and partners also pursue research via protocols almost certain to have some overlap with the geochemistry community.

Figure 1: Highlighted United Nations Sustainable Development Goals to which Geochemical Data directly relates.

2. Rationale, Structure and Activities

Currently the OneGeochemistry initiative is informal and run by the [OneGeochemistry Interim Board](#) (Lehnert et al., 2022). The interim board decided that the initiative should become formalised as the **OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group** for the next two years from the time of writing. As the Committee on Data of the International Science Council (ISC), it was judged that CODATA provided the appropriate institutional home for this Working Group because of its engagement with a number of relevant initiatives, with the data activities in various domains and with the International Scientific Unions that are members of ISC.

This CODATA Working Group for Geochemistry will be the basis for international and sole focus on the data component of geochemistry. As a CODATA Working Group, the OneGeochemistry initiative will set up its governance structure to be organised in a democratic system backed by terms of reference led by a chair and co-chair and will form expert advisory groups where required.

Currently, there are few standards that ensure compliance of geochemical data with the FAIR principles. It is not just a matter of coordinating the geochemical community per se; what is also

required is close collaboration with leading informatics communities and initiatives that are developing modern data infrastructures and/or data standards, vocabularies and other semantic resources that ensure compliance with the FAIR principles and enable data to be accessed by machines.

Partner organisations and participants will be able to provide input to the Working Group through its Slack channel, and through meetings, workshops and general assemblies. Partners to OneGeochemistry can be professional societies, science unions, science associations/commissions, publishers, funding agencies, analytical data repositories, industry, government, academia, research and not-for-profit organisations or departments, research groups and/or projects: all are welcome to join.

Within the greater framework of the WorldFAIR project, this deliverable has come together in collaboration with [CODATA](#)^c (WP01 and WP02) and [IUPAC](#)ⁱ (WP03) while building upon global examples from the [OneGeology initiative](#)^o, Earth System Information Partners ([ESIP](#))^{es}, the [Genomics Standards Consortium](#)^{ge} and the [IUSSP CODATA Working Group](#)^{iu}.

The OneGeochemistry initiative provided CODATA with the following Terms of Reference as part of their application to become the **OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group**:

Introduction

The OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group's mission is to advance geoscientific knowledge and discoveries by building and maintaining consensus-driven standards that make geochemistry research data globally findable and accessible, and truly interoperable and reusable to both humans and machines.

OneGeochemistry seeks to create a global geochemical data network that facilitates and promotes discovery of, and access to, geochemical data through coordination and collaboration among international geochemical data providers by:

1. Engaging global communities to create and maintain international standards, vocabularies and best practice documents for geochemical techniques and analytes;
2. Publishing these community-agreed standards, vocabularies and best practices in a format that makes geochemical data globally FAIR and enables direct access and interpretation by machines for computational analysis and modelling; and

3. Providing standards and best practice guidelines to record provenance, methodology and a measure of data quality that will enable users to trust, interpret and reuse data.

Rationale

Geochemical data have applications in many disciplines including geology, cosmology, environment, resources (groundwater, minerals, energy), geohealth, ocean and agriculture. As such, geochemical data play an important role in at least six of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. To support these disciplines and goals, there is a growing need to provide advice and support the implementation of data quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) validation methods for laboratories, repositories, publishers and policy makers. When provenance, methodology and a measure of data quality are consistently documented others will be enabled to trust, interpret and reuse data. In enabling and simplifying the (re)use of geochemical data, OneGeochemistry will help to facilitate acceleration of the generation of new geoscientific knowledge and discoveries.

As OneGeochemistry organises collaboration and coordination of data reporting standardisation efforts that are non-unique across the diverse geochemistry communities, this initiative fills a niche previously unoccupied. Standardisation efforts have always focused on national, programmatic or less centralised levels. The formalisation of OneGeochemistry and endorsement by societies and associations will enable the initiative to develop and promote influential, community-driven data conventions and best practices necessary to build a global network of high-quality, trusted geochemical data. These actions will enable FAIRer geochemical data, simplifying data (re)use which will both contribute to many UN Sustainable Development goals and accelerate the generation of new geoscientific knowledge and discoveries.

Work Plan

During the two years as CODATA Working Group, OneGeochemistry will focus on Community Building (engaging with partners and participants, forming expert working groups, and expanding efforts to seek endorsement of unions, societies, commissions and associations; in especially the first half year of WG formation), Generation of Common Vocabularies (through formation of expert working groups and collaboration between existing initiatives) and Generation of FIPs and Recommendations (of geochemistry data reporting). The OneGeochemistry Initiative has sent out a formal letter seeking endorsement to several geochemical associations, commissions and societies. Once endorsed by these societies OneGeochemistry will extend an invitation to experts

from these and the wider geochemistry community to join expert groups in early 2023. One expert group will be charged to develop common vocabularies and another expert group will where possible build upon existing or else generate new recommendations towards geochemical data reporting. Firstly, common vocabularies for both geochemical techniques and analytes will be created by the geochemistry community (e.g. for XRF and ICP-MS, elemental concentrations and U–Pb isotopes). These vocabularies will be developed in consultation and collaboration with other initiatives and groups that are well advanced in the development of digital data standards that both ensure compliance with FAIR and also enable interoperability of geochemical data with the other 10 Work Packages of the WorldFAIR project. These initiatives and groups include the [International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry \(IUPAC\)](#) and their ‘[Colour Books](#)’; [CODATA DDI-CDI Cross Domain Integration Initiative](#); the [CODATA Digital Representation of Units of Measure \(DRUM\) Task Group](#); and relevant [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#) groups (e.g., [Vocabulary Services Interest Group](#); [Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences Interest Group](#); etc): these efforts will be aligned with the ‘[10 Simple Rules](#)’ for making a vocabulary FAIR. These FAIR vocabularies are to be published through [Research Vocabularies Australia \(RVA\)](#) and will serve as examples on how to build and publish further geochemistry subdiscipline specific vocabularies.

Through the CODATA Working Group, and as part of the [CODATA-led WorldFAIR Project](#), OneGeochemistry aims to engage and motivate community repositories and databases to share their FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) in a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP). From the various FIPs, common FERs can be extracted to be published (after about a year into the WG) that will help repositories and databases to become more FAIR (especially facilitating interoperability). The publication of vocabularies, FIPs and geochemistry data reporting recommendations will allow the community to use and consider them for QA/QC of geochemical datasets published in the literature.

3. Conclusion

Due to the increasing volume of geochemical data, there is a significant need for greater collaboration and coordination of the diverse geochemistry community. A formal OneGeochemistry initiative can create a governance structure upon which the initiative can build into the future as well as engage and connect with key stakeholders from the global community. Becoming the OneGeochemistry CODATA Working Group will give OneGeochemistry credibility and authority to successfully pursue long-term governance structure and enable OneGeochemistry to develop and

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promote influential, global, community-driven data conventions and best practices necessary to build a global network of high-quality, trusted geochemical data.

4. Bibliography and web resources

^aAuScope Geochemistry Network - AusGeochem, Australian-produced geochemistry data from around the globe, <https://www.auscope.org.au/ausgeochem>

^cCODATA, International Science Council Committee on DATA, <https://codata.org/>

^dDigital Geochemical Data Infrastructure (DIGIS) for GEOROC 2.0, <https://georoc.eu/>

^eEarthChem, search and contribute geochemical data, <https://www.earthchem.org/>

^{ep}EPOS - European Plate Observing System, Integrates national and transnational research infrastructures for solid Earth science, <https://www.epos-eu.org/>

^{es}Earth System Information Partners, <https://www.esipfed.org/>

^gGFZ Data Services, <https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/portal/>

^gGenomics Standards Consortium, <https://www.genesc.org/>

ⁱIUPAC, <https://iupac.org/>

^{iu}IUSSP CODATA Working Group, <https://codata.org/initiatives/decadal-programme2/fair-vocabularies/iussp-codata-working-group-on-fair-vocabularies/>

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ⁿNFDI4Earth, NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences, <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/>

^oOneGeology Initiative, <https://onegeology.org/about/governance.html>

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<https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

5. Appendix 1

International Science Unions, Societies, Associations and Commissions that either collect geochemical data and/or are developing standards that are relevant to OneGeochemistry

- 1) Science Unions:
 - a) International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG)
 - b) International Union of Geological Sciences (IUGS)
 - c) International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC)
 - d) International Union of Crystallography (IUCr)
 - e) International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS)
- 2) Associations, Commissions and Programs that are directly attached to Science Unions
 - a) IUGG: International Association of the Volcanology and Chemistry of the Earth's Interior (IAVCEI) of the IUGG.
 - b) IUGS: Commission for the Management and Application of Geoscience Information (CGI)
 - c) IUGS: Deep-time Digital Earth Big Science Program (DDE)
 - d) IUGS: Commission on Global Geochemical Baselines (GCB)
- 3) Independent Societies and Associations that are independent of Science Unions. Note: many have informal affiliations with the Unions.
 - a) The Geochemical Society (GS)
 - b) The European Association of Geochemistry (EAG)
 - c) The International Association of GeoChemistry (IAGC)
 - d) The International Association of Geoanalysts (IAG)
 - e) The Association of Applied Geochemists (AAG)
 - f) The Society for Environmental Geochemistry and Health (SEGH)
 - g) The Meteoritical Society